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Project: “#bookstagram and beyond. Towards a domain-attuned sentiment mining of the evaluative talk of literature generated by literary prizes”

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Thematic strand: 3

Abstract:

In this paper, we aim to present the design and some preliminary results of the new FWO-funded research project “Evaluation of literature by professional and layperson critics. A digital and literary sociological analysis of evaluative talk of literature through the prism of literary prizes (2007-2017)”, which will run from 2019 to 2023. The project’s main ambition is to comparatively analyse and mine the “talk of literature” surrounding six prominent literary prizes in three different languages. For this purpose, a fine-grained sentiment analysis approach will be used, namely Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA), to detect not only whether a positive or negative valuation is being expressed, but also to discover whether a specific “aspect” (book, juror, institution, etc.) is regarded in a positive, neutral or negative way. As a consequence, the focal point will be the talk of literature as a network phenomenon and not just the discussion of literary quality itself.

Although there has been ample empirical and theoretical research on the ‘field(s)’ of literary criticism and its changing institutional context, few scholars (e.g. Kellermann et al 2016) have actually attempted to directly ingest and mine the actual content of user-generated online literary criticism. While there is no shortage of broad trend watching, predicting and apocalyptic doom saying (activities that seem to be endemic to literary criticism itself), the actual scope and productivity of phenomena like #bookstagram and activist counter-criticism like #diekanon and #frauenzählen (#countingwomen) remain largely unknown. Recent studies (Schneider 2018; Kempke/Vöcklinghaus/Zeh 2019, Chong, 2020) mainly evoke institutions under threat and take the vantage point of professional literary critics and their uncertainties. However, little attention has been paid to layman literary criticism itself, its frames of reference and the effect of peer-to-peer recommendation systems as a novel way of gatekeeping access to the literary system.

The NLP tools developed in this project aim to tackle a number of technical challenges raised by the project: On the one hand, literary criticism is lexicalised to a much lesser extent

than other domains which have hitherto been the main target of sentiment mining (e.g. “the new iPhone is very cool”). On the other hand, the specific setting of users meta-commenting on what they perceive as “official literary criticism” calls for both a role-sensitive, quasi-narratological approach (cf. Martens 2020) and an estimate of the extent in which lay and professional critics converge and diverge (Lacante 2018). Hence, the corpus consists of a wide variety of sources and is excerpted from both “old” media, such as literary journals, the jury reports of the literary prizes and reviews in professional publications, as well as from “new” media, such as the reader impressions and “sentiments” expressed on social networks like Goodreads, Twitter and Instagram. In terms of technological setup, we extend a sentiment mining pipeline developed in-house with multilingualism in mind. (Van de Kauter et al. 2013)

The project’s methodology is relevant to any field drawing on ‘the wisdom of the crowds’. The digitisation of the public sphere has led to a proliferation of the agents and media (both digital and traditional) participating in the evaluative talk about literature (Allington, 2016). These new gatekeepers are not just emotionally involved in the discussion, they are increasingly recruited and involved by the literary system itself. Thus, the knowledge of a limited number of professional ‘pundits’ is being rivalled and challenged by technological developments and the reliance on a type of “distributed cognition” even more urgently in need of exploration.

We posit that each of these media implements a distinct way of communicating that comes with certain expectations and limitations regarding length, register, the subject of the critical discourse etc.. As the range of (social) media platforms used by both these professional and layperson critics alike to express their opinions and sentiments concerning the valuation of literature and of the competing literary works is increasingly heterogeneous and multimodal, follow-up research could also take in to account paralinguistic aspects of online literary criticism and debate.

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